

Extremal Properties in Kinetic Studies

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Solvent effects on some equilibrium and kinetic properties often show extremal behaviour if water constitutes a component of the binary. While ΔH^\ddagger and $T\Delta S^\ddagger$ generally exhibit stationary behaviour in the highly aquated composition of the binary in the acid hydrolysis of esters, in alkaline hydrolysis, such maxima in ΔH^\ddagger may or may not occur. Furthermore, the peaks in rate constant values, k , which are infrequently observed, result from lack of complete obedience to the usual mirror image relationship curves of ΔH^\ddagger and $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$. Observation of such extremal features in kinetics has been made here in acid hydrolyses of *t*-butylacetate in methanol-water and DMSO-water systems and in alkaline hydrolyses of cinnamates in ethanol-water binary.

MANY of the intrinsic characteristics of kinetics of reactions are revealed only when organo-aqueous binaries are used as solvent media. One such effect which attracted the attention of the investigators in the sixties only was the exhibition of stationary values of ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and rather infrequently of peaks of 'k' values, with variation of the solvent composition. Such results have been reported by Arnett and Mckelvey¹ and Winstein and Fainberg² for ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger in solvolysis reactions and also for 'k' by Roy and Das³ and Khalil and Sadek⁴ in hydrolysis reactions. The extremal properties are, however, almost a regular feature in respect of equilibrium properties, such as enthalpies of solutions of solutes^{5,6} in organo-aqueous binaries.

We discuss below only the relevant activation parameter data for acid hydrolysis of *t*-butylacetate in $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}/\text{water}$ and alkaline hydrolysis of a few substituted and unsubstituted cinnamate esters in $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}/\text{water}$ medium and complement it with a generalized discussion pertinent to the occurrence of stationary values or peak values of kinetic parameters. Result of a limited study at a single temp. (30°) for acid hydrolysis of *t*-butylacetate in DMSO/water is graphically represented as a supporting proof for the occurrence of rate constant peak.

Two plots, one of 'k' values versus mole fraction of water in the acid hydrolysis set and the other of ΔH^\ddagger as function of mole fraction in the acid hydrolysis of *t*-butylacetate as well as alkaline hydrolysis of the cinnamates are provided to furnish examples of peaks or of maximal behaviour. The ΔH^\ddagger values, as plotted, represent the mean of repetitive experiments and the uncertainty in their values are ± 250 cal/mole, the total span of uncertainty being 500 cal/mole. A logical discussion of the result has much in common with those of the equilibrium properties in organo-aqueous binaries. Of these, the most-quoted is the partial enthalpy of solutions, $\Delta \bar{H}_S$, of electrolytes and non-electrolytes in the binaries. The general contention is that the exhibition of maximum in $\Delta \bar{H}_S$ is intimately related

to the structuredness¹⁰ of liquid water. Addition of organic component to water at first aids structure promotion and further addition beyond a limit abets its demolition^{7,8}. When electrolytes or non-electrolytes are added to such binaries, already possessed of certain structuredness, the solute molecules enter into the competitive fray for construction of solvent structures around them. Thus two thermal effects one, endothermic, involved in the breaking of the structural units of water and the other, exothermic, associated with the structure formation around the added solutes accompany this process. This endothermic effect peaks at the binary composition of maximum structuredness and decreases on either side of it resulting in a maximum in the trace of $\Delta \bar{H}_S$ against mole fraction. Unlike the equilibrium property, viz. the $\Delta \bar{H}_S$, a kinetic parameter, say ΔH^\ddagger , will be given at any composition of the binary by a difference of the partial molar enthalpy of solution, ($\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{tr}}$) of the transition state and that of the ground state, ($\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{g}}$) of the reactant or reactants in the given binary medium. Hence, referred to an extremely dilute aqueous solution as the standard state, the medium effect on the enthalpy of activation is

$$\delta_M(\Delta H^\ddagger) = (\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{tr}})_W^M - (\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{g}})_W^M \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where the right-hand side terms represent the enthalpies of transfer from water to the given medium of the transition state and of the ground state respectively.

The free energy of transfer of an ion from water to a binary medium $\delta_M(\Delta F)$ i.e., $(\Delta F)_W^M$ consists of four contributions

$$(\Delta F)_W^M = (\Delta F_{\text{st}})_W^M + (\Delta F_{\text{prt}})_W^M + (\Delta F_{\text{sec}})_W^M + (\Delta F_{\text{B}})_W^M \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where, the right hand side terms, taken in order, are contributions arising from (i) preliminary structural entropy changes due to breaking or strengthening of hydrogen bonds, (ii) differences in energies of primary solvation in water and in

organic medium, (iii) differences in secondary solvation and (iv) Born solvation energy difference in the two dielectric continua. The first part $(\Delta F_{st})_W^M$ is usually small (vide Feakins⁹) and neglected. The second component, $(\Delta F_{pri})_W^M$, is negative for positive ions and vice versa—a conclusion supported by experimental data. $(\Delta F_{sec})_W^M$ and $(\Delta F_B)_W^M$ are both positive. Thus the last three terms constitute the electrical contributions toward the single ion free energy transfer. Corresponding to each of such free energy transfer component there is an enthalpy of transfer term. In order to interpret our result and the other generally observed results we make the assumption that $(\Delta H_{pri})_W^M$, $(\Delta H_{sec})_W^M$ and $(\Delta H_B)_W^M$ are of the same sign as their free energy counterparts. This assumption is not completely arbitrary but bears the implication that the changes in entropies of solvation of the ground state and the activated state are not very large.

In the hydrolysis of our esters, H^+ or OH^- ions are involved and the transition states are, according to the accepted mechanisms of ester hydrolysis, charged species in both the cases. Hence eq. (1), in the background of eq. (2), can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_M(\Delta H^\ddagger) &= (\Delta \bar{H}_S^{tr})_W^M - (\Delta \bar{H}_S^g)_W^M \\ &= (\Delta \bar{H}_S^{tr})_W^M - (\Delta \bar{H}_S^{ester})_W^M - (\Delta \bar{H}_S^{cat})_W^M \\ &= \{(\Delta H_{pri}^{tr})_W^M + (\Delta H_{sec}^{tr})_W^M + (\Delta H_B^{tr})_W^M\} - \\ &\quad \{(\Delta H_{pri}^{ester})_W^M + (\Delta H_{sec}^{ester})_W^M + (\Delta H_B^{ester})_W^M\} - \\ &\quad \{(\Delta H_{pri}^{cat})_W^M + (\Delta H_{sec}^{cat})_W^M + (\Delta H_B^{cat})_W^M\} \quad \dots (3) \end{aligned}$$

where the superscript 'cat' represents the catalyst H^+ ions or OH^- ions depending on the acid or base catalysed hydrolysis of the ester. Let us consider the acid hydrolysis of tertiary butyl acetate and the corresponding curves for 'k' (Fig. 1) which are divided into segments ab and bc. Of all the components in eq. (3), the primary solvation terms are

Fig. 1. ' k_{sp} (litre mole⁻¹ min⁻¹) vs 'mole fraction of solvent component' plot for acid hydrolysis of *t*-butylacetate. A, B, C—solvent-methanol/water; 30°, 40° and 45° respectively. D—solvent-DMSO/water, 30°.

the most important (especially so in the highly aquated regions of the binaries) with the secondary solvation and the Born terms gaining more importance as the water content in the binaries goes on decreasing. Remembering that the activated complex in acid hydrolysis is a positively charged complex, the magnitude of $(\Delta H_S^{tr})_W^M$ along the highly aquated region, a to b, will be mainly controlled by the endothermicity associated with increasing amount of splitting of the structuredness of water in the binaries and the exothermicity of $(\Delta H_{pri}^{tr})_W^M$. Insignificant endothermic contributions also arise from $(\Delta H_{sec}^{tr})_W^M$ and $(\Delta H_B^{tr})_W^M$. The endothermicity will be maximum in the region of maximum structuredness (mole fraction of water 0.72 in CH_3OH/H_2O binary and 0.82 in $DMSO/H_2O$ binary¹⁰) and just beyond this region endothermicity will gradually wane and $(\Delta H_{pri}^{tr})_W^M$ will have an edge in final analysis. The result will be a maximum for $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{tr})_W^M$. Similar nature of enthalpic changes with individual peaks for ground state reactants viz. $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{ester})_W^M$ and $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{cat})_W^M$ will occur in the region around b. It is known that the endothermic effect¹⁰ associated with the breaking of structures is more for the neutral ester than it is for a charged species, viz. the transition state complex or the catalytic H^+ ions. Hence when the difference represented by eq. (3) is taken for a plot of ΔH^\ddagger against mole fraction, a dip or minimum is expected in the region b. A little beyond the point b, the endothermic influences of $(\Delta H_{sec}^{tr})_W^M$ and $(\Delta H_B^{tr})_W^M$ will outweigh the $(\Delta H_{pri}^{tr})_W^M$ owing to increased amount of organic component of lower dielectric constant. Similar considerations will apply to the reactants viz. the ester and the catalytic ions.

It is found to show a maximum at 0.74 mole fraction of water in CH_3OH/H_2O and at 0.92 mole fraction in $DMSO/H_2O$ binaries (Fig. 1). The corresponding mole fraction values for maximum structure are 0.72 and 0.82 of water in the two binaries. The maximum in the ' k ' value had in the past been sometimes wrongly attributed⁴ to the availability of more solvent (water) molecules, consequent on structure break-down by organic component, for solvation of the more polarised activated complex. In view of what has been discussed in terms of conducive effect on promotion of structure by initial addition of organic component, this interpretation is patently wrong.

The shift in the position of the minimum in the plot of ΔH^\ddagger [or maximum in the plot of k] from the maximum structure composition of the binary solvent will depend greatly on whether one or more than one reactant (including the catalyst) is involved. In the one reactant case, such as solvolysis of

t-butylchloride (S_N1 mechanism) the minimum in ΔH^\ddagger is almost at the maximum structure composition¹⁰. But in acid hydrolysis of esters, since two enthalpic terms, $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{ester}})_W^M$ and $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{cat}})_W^M$ are involved for the reactants, the minimum in ΔH^\ddagger , decided ultimately by the point-to-point difference of eq. (3), may or may not occur just at the composition of maximum structure of the binary solvent. This is indeed found in the hydrolysis of *t*-butylacetate in DMSO/ H_2O binary where the shift is roughly 0.1 mole fraction. This is one point where the extremal behaviour of a kinetic property in binary solvent may show a difference from the equilibrium or spectral property¹⁰ in the same binary solvent.

In the alkaline hydrolyses of the cinnamates and the substituted cinnamates, ΔH^\ddagger shows distinct minima in Fig. 2A and B and a tendency for a minimum in Fig. 2C, where investigation into higher aqueous-content side was not feasible for reasons of solubility. Unlike the acid hydrolysis,

Fig. 2. ' ΔH^\ddagger ' vs 'mole fraction of water' plot for alkaline hydrolyses of cinnamates in ethanol-water and acid hydrolysis of *t*-butylacetate in methanol-water. A—Ethyl cinnamate, B—Ethyl *p*-methoxy cinnamate, C—Ethyl *p*-methyl cinnamate, D—*t*-Butylacetate.

the transition state here is negatively charged and hence single ion free energy (and hence enthalpy) transfer term is positive⁹. Accordingly $(\Delta H_{\text{prt}}^{\text{tr}})_W^M$, $(\Delta H_{\text{sec}}^{\text{tr}})_W^M$ and $(\Delta H_{\text{B}}^{\text{tr}})_W^M$ are all endothermic. Hence maximisation of $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{tr}})_W^M$ of equation (3) is not guaranteed. The $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{ester}})_W^M$ and $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{cat}})_W^M$ for the reactants will also individually behave in the same way. Hence, there will hardly be any chance for the heat of activation ΔH^\ddagger , given as the difference of $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{tr}})_W^M$ and $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{ester}})_W^M$ plus $(\Delta \bar{H}_S^{\text{cat}})_W^M$, to exhibit

any minimum at least in the highly aquated side. But as argued earlier, the exhibition of minimum in ΔH^\ddagger , depends on the point-to-point difference of the three quantities of eq. (3) and not just on the individual absolute values of the three enthalpic terms just mentioned. If the point-to-point difference favours any such minimal dip in the ΔH^\ddagger plot, it is expected to be far shifted from the composition of the maximum structure of the binary. It happens to be so in the alkaline hydrolyses of the cinnamates and the substituted cinnamates where minima are located at the binary solvent composition of around 0.6 mole fraction of water, the maximum structure composition being 0.85 for C_2H_5OH/H_2O binary¹¹. Instances involving the alkaline decarboxylation of trichloroacetate ion by Diefallah and coworkers in methanol/water¹² and ethanol/water¹³ can be cited where the minima in ΔH^\ddagger are present and absent respectively. In the former case¹² minima occurs at 0.6 mole fraction of water. Minima in ΔH^\ddagger was also observed by Costeanu and Landauer¹⁴ in acid hydrolysis of butyl formate and acetate at about 0.8 mole fraction of water. Another case of considerable shift of the composition reflecting extrema was reported by Mondal and Lahiri¹⁵ where maxima in ρ (reaction constant) values were obtained at 0.5 and 0.6 mole fraction of water respectively in methanol/water and ethanol/water binaries. ΔH^\ddagger minimum in the alkaline hydrolysis of esters is neither totally expected nor unexpected. But in acid hydrolysis the minimal behaviour is more or less expected on the highly aquated side of the binary.

Extremal natures of $T\Delta S^\ddagger$, ΔF^\ddagger and k : It will suffice to say that wherever ΔH^\ddagger shows a minimum, $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$ exhibits a maximum. ΔH^\ddagger and $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$ often have twin mirror-image profiles. The causality of such a mirror-image relation between ΔH^\ddagger and $-T\Delta S^\ddagger$ is the kinetic parameter ΔF^\ddagger and along with it k , the rate constant. The most expected variation of ΔF^\ddagger or ' k ' with solvent composition is one of monotonicity. It is only when the mirror-image profiles do not completely match, that there arises the possibility of ΔF^\ddagger showing a shallow minimum resulting in maximum of ' k '. Maxima in ' k ' values, as in tertiary butylacetate hydrolysis, are exceptions rather than the rule, although minimum in ΔH^\ddagger is a natural expectation in acid hydrolysis of esters with changing composition of the solvent.

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